

The Role of Oro-Pharyngeal - Oesophageal – Scintigraphy in Evaluation of Stroke Patients for Starting on Oral Feed, in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Madurai: An Observational Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Dysphagia is a common complication of stroke and is a major risk factor for developing aspiration pneumonia. Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy, helps to access functional aspects and it is also a semi-quantitative study of the various stages of swallowing, it can also detect tracheobronchial aspiration. Hence the study is done to assess the role of Oro-Pharyngeal – Oesophageal Scintigraphy in the evaluation of stroke patients for starting on oral feed.

Materials and Methods: This observational study was done among 60 stroke patients who passed water swallow test, in a tertiary care hospital, Madurai, for the period of two months from December 2023 – January 2024 and Oro – Pharyngeal – Oesophageal scintigraphy was done after administrating 5mci of Tc99m Sulphur colloid mixed with semi solid instant cereal food.

Results and Discussion: 30% of stroke patients showed signs of aspiration in Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy even though they have passed the water swallow test. Mean of Oral transit time (1.1s), Pharyngeal transit time (1.7s), Oesophageal transit time (16s), Retention index- oropharyngeal region (7.55%) and oesophageal region (26.15%) has increased in the study participants than the normal. There was a statistically significant (p value-0.000) increase in these parameters among patients those who had aspiration than those who did not had aspiration. Percentage of oesophageal emptying at 10sec has decreased in the study participants than the normal and there was a statistically significant (p value-0.003) decrease in this parameter among those who had aspiration than those who did not had aspiration. Mean aspiration rate in our study was 31.6%.

Conclusion: Evaluation of swallowing in assessing readiness to start oral feeds in stroke patients can be done using Oro-Pharyngeal – Oesophageal scintigraphy in canters with gamma Camera.

Keywords: Dysphagia, Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal Scintigraphy, Aspiration Pneumonia, Water Swallow Test.

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Introduction

According to world stroke organization globally around 12.2 million new strokes cases are reported per year and 101 million people are currently living, who have experienced stroke. [1] In India prevalence rate of stroke including both urban and rural population varies from 44.54 to 150/100000 and incidence rate varies from 33 to 123/100000 [2]

Dysphagia is a common complication of stroke and is a major risk factor for developing aspiration pneumonia. Dysphagia related to stroke is more precisely characterized as Oro- pharyngeal dysphagia, defined by swallowing impairment of

the upper digestive tract. In a study done by Tungkaserirak et al. among 245 acute stroke patients 45.6% of patients had swallowing disorders, and abnormal swallowing was significantly associated with occurrence of pneumonia (OR=3.1, 95% CI=1.2-8.1, p=0.01) [3]. Dysphagia not only leads to aspiration but also causes malnutrition, weight loss, dehydration and decreased quality of life. [4,5] Early diagnosis will play a key role in preventing aspiration pneumonia. [6]

Simple bed side tests like “Water swallow test” is used to assess readiness to swallow but is less

accurate. [7] Videofluoroscopic swallowing study is considered to be gold standard in picking up aspiration. This technique provides dynamic imaging of the swallowing and visualizing the bolus during the process of swallowing by adding contrast material like barium sulphate to food bolus. However there is risk of radiation exposure [8]. Flexible endoscopic examination of oropharyngeal swallowing (FEES) requires passage of flexible laryngoscope into the hypopharynx and visualization of food bolus with dye. But is an invasive procedure and requires skilled operator. Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy, helps to access functional aspects and it is also a semi-quantitative study of the various stages of swallowing, it can also detect tracheobronchial aspiration. It is also safe and non-invasive. [9] Hence the study is done with the following objective

Objective: To assess the role of Oro-Pharyngeal – Oesophageal Scintigraphy in the evaluation of stroke patients for starting oral feed.

Materials and Methods

An observational study was done among stroke patients admitted in a tertiary care hospital, Madurai. The study was conducted for the period of two months from December 2023 – January 2023. Stroke patients who were on nasogastric feeding, alert, awake and who have passed water swallow test was included in the study. According to the study done by Grosso et al mean aspiration rate for tracheal aspiration was 18.1% and mean aspiration rate for broncho-pulmonary aspiration was 44.9%⁹, taking lowest value for sample size calculation with P as 18.1%, q as 81.9%, z= 1.96, absolute precision as 10% and non-response rate as 20% sample size calculated using the formula $Z^2 \frac{PQ}{L^2}$ was 62. Patient who did not give informed consent and who failed water swallowing test were excluded from the study. Finally, 60 stroke patients satisfying the inclusion criteria were recruited through convenient sampling technique.

Institutional ethical clearance and informed consent of the participants were got. Confidentiality of the patients were maintained throughout the study. Study tool was predesigned 'semi-structured questionnaire to collect basic details and stroke details; water swallow test and Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy.

Water Swallow test:

- Stroke patient must be awake and alert
- Patient was positioned upright in bed as high as tolerated between 30 to 90 degrees.

- Instructed to drink 100ml of water from cup by mouth or using straw slowly and steadily without stopping.
- The test is passed if the patient is able to drink the entire volume of water without coughing or choking during or within one minute of swallowing.

Oro – Pharyngeal – Oesophageal scintigraphy: 5mci of Tc99m sulphur colloid was mixed with semi solid instant cereal food. Patient was made to consume radionuclide colloid admixed semisolid food orally over 30 minutes in sitting position under the gamma camera (anterior and posterior projections) while dynamic imaging was done with frame rate of 15 seconds per frame, followed by static image of oral cavity, thorax and upper abdomen in the field of view. Radiotracer activity was monitored in serial intervals of 15mins for one hour. Presence of radiotracer activity in tracheobronchial tree or lung parenchyma was considered as induce of aspiration.

Parameters studied [10]

1. **Oral transit time:** After the patient swallows the time required for the bolus to pass and leave the oral cavity. (Normally less than 1 second)
2. **Pharyngeal Transit Time:** The time required for the bolus to pass and leave the Pharynx. It is the time interval between entry and exit of bolus in the pharynx. (Normally less than 1.2 second)
3. **Oesophageal Transit Time:** The time required for the bolus to pass and leave the oesophagus. It is the time interval between entry and exit of bolus in the oesophagus. (Normally less than 10 second)
4. **Retention index:** This is the quantity of bolus 10 seconds after swallowing (normally less than 5% in Oro-pharyngeal region and less than 20% in oesophagus).
5. **Percentage of oesophageal emptying at 10 seconds:**

$$= [(E_{\max} - E_{10\text{sec}})/E_{\max}] \times 100,$$

E_{\max} - maximum amount of oesophageal radioactivity uptake,

$E_{10\text{s}}$ - radioactivity in the oesophagus 10 seconds after the maximum peak of the activity. (Normally 80%).

6. Aspiration rate:

$$= RA \times 100 / (AT - AT2).$$

RA – radioactivity in aspiration area

AT- radioactivity in oral cavity before swallowing

AT2 – residual radioactivity after swallowing

Chart 1: Flow chart

Data were entered in Microsoft excel and analysis done using SPSS software version 23.

Descriptive statistics was used to find frequencies, percentages, rates, mean and standard deviation.

Means between two groups were compared by independent sample t test and p value <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results:

Out of 60 stroke patients who underwent Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy 39 were females and 21 were males.

Majority of them (36.67%) belong to the age group 70 to 75 years.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the age and sex of the stroke patients who underwent Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy

Table 1: Age and sex of the study population (n = 60)

Age (years)	Male- n (%)	Female- n (%)	Total
<60	2 (3.33%)	1(1.67%)	3 (5%)
61-65	7(11.67%)	8(13.33%)	15(25%)
66-70	7(11.67%)	10(16.66%)	17(28.33%)
71-75	9(15%)	13(21.67%)	22(36.67%)
>75	1(1.67%)	2(3.33%)	3(5%)
Total	21(35%)	39(65%)	60(100%)

Table 2 depicts the co-morbidities among the stroke patients studied. 32 of them were hypertensives, 10 of them were diabetics, 14 of them were both diabetic and hypertensives and 4 of them were hypertensives with diabetes and chronic kidney disease.

Table 2: Distribution of comorbidities among the study population (n =60)

Comorbidities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Diabetes mellitus	10	16.66
Hypertension	32	53.33
Diabetes and hypertension	14	23.33
Hypertension, diabetes and CKD	4	6.67
Total	60	100

Figure 1 portrays the types of the stroke among our study population. Majority of them had ischemic stroke (46%). Figure 2 gives the aspiration among the study population. 30% of stroke patients who had passed water swallowing test and then subjected to Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy showed signs of aspiration.

Figure 1: Distribution of type of stroke among the study population (n =60)

Figure 2: Signs of aspiration among stroke patients who underwent Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy (n=60)

42 patients who did not show the signs of aspiration in Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy were successfully started on oral feeds and were followed up for 2 months, for clinical and radiological evidence of aspiration. None of the 42 patients started on oral feeds had evidence of aspiration at the end of 2 months follow up. Table 3 shows the comparison of various parameters studied between those who showed and does not show aspiration signs in Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy. Overall Mean of all the parameters like transit time and retention and

aspiration rate were higher than the normal in stroke patients. Oesophageal emptying rate in 10 seconds was lower than the normal in stroke patients. There was more deviation in all the parameters from normal among those who showed signs of aspiration than those who did not show any signs of aspiration. Means between two groups were compared by independent sample t test and statistically significant difference was found between means of all the parameters between two groups.

Table 3: Comparison of various parameters studied between those who showed and does not show aspiration (n=60)

Parameters	Mean of all the participants (n=60)	Do not show signs of aspiration(n=42) Mean (SD)	shows signs of aspiration(n=18) Mean (SD)	p-value	t value
Oral transit time	1.1 seconds	1 seconds (0.2)	1.3 seconds (0.4)	0.000	-3.883
Pharyngeal transit time	1.7 seconds	1.3 seconds (0.6)	2.1 seconds (0.7)	0.000	-4.5
Oesophageal transit time	16 seconds	12 seconds (2.2)	20 seconds (3.6)	0.000	-10.56
Retention index- oropharyngeal region	7.55%	5.5% (1.3%)	9.6% (1.9%)	0.000	-9.69
Retention index – oesophageal region	26.15%	21% (3.4%)	31.3% (5%)	0.000	-9.28
Percentage of oesophageal emptying at 10 sec	72.5%	78% (12%)	67% (15%)	0.003	3.014
Aspiration rate	31.62%	0%	31.62% (10%)	0.000	-20.71

Discussion

Among 60 stroke patients who were included in the study 30% of them showed signs of aspiration in Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy even though they have passed the water swallow test. This was lower than in the study done by Grosso M et al [9] among neurological patients were 60% of them showed signs of aspiration. Mean of Oral transit time (1.1s), Pharyngeal transit time(1.7s), Oesophageal transit time(16s), Retention index- oropharyngeal region(7.55%) and oesophageal region (26.15%) has increased in the study participants than the normal but this result was different from the study done by Silva et al [11] where pharyngeal transit time was 0.48s which was shorter than the normal controls but there was increase in the oral retention index (18.4 %) than normal controls which was similar to the present study. There was a statistically significant increase in these parameters among patients those who had aspiration than those who did not had aspiration. Percentage of oesophageal emptying at 10sec has decreased in the study participants than the normal and there was a statistically significant decrease in this parameter among those who had aspiration than those who did not had aspiration. Mean aspiration rate in our study was 31.6% this was similar to other study done by Grosso M et al [9] where tracheal aspiration was 18.1% and bronchopulmonary aspiration was 44.9%, In the research two tests, water swallow test and Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy were done in series. The stroke patients who passed water swallow test also underwent Oro-Pharyngeal-Oesophageal scintigraphy, so chance of false positive was very much reduced and it also proved that none of the 42 patients started on oral feeds had evidence of aspiration at the end of 2 months follow up. But however, the limitation of this study is lack of comparison with the gold standard tool. But this study act as the base for future higher studies with large sample size.

Conclusion

Evaluation of swallowing in assessing readiness to start oral feeds in stroke patients can be done using Oro-Pharyngeal – Oesophageal scintigraphy in canters with gamma Camera. It is a safe procedure and better than water swallow test. Has reduced radiation exposure, Physiological as the radiotracer can be admixed with patient's regular diet, non-invasive and assesses all the phases of swallowing

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